

PLATELET RICH PLASMA THERAPY FOR SKIN REJUVENATION**Bharath Raja**

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Platelet Rich Plasma [PRP] therapy is one of the most attention gained treatment among the people worldwide for their intense ability to rejuvenate the skin which got deteriorated due to injuries, ageing and also it has been used for hair loss. It is a minimally invasive technique which improves texture, tightening and elasticity of the skin .It works on the principle of harvesting our own blood and maximizing the concentrations of platelet and the growth factors, then injected trans dermally to give a desired effect of rejuvenation with a better benefit to risk ratio. This is the reason behind it of calling this therapy as “**Vampire facial**”.

Purpose of study :

As the concern over the skin care got increased among the people over the past two decades, tells us the importance of study of PRP therapy for skin rejuvenation. It is well tolerated due to its autologous nature compared to other invasive cosmetic procedures.

Materials and methods :

This abstract is primarily written on the basis of several research-based articles and literature review to get a different view over this topic. Comparative analytical results were used to provide a better and clear view of this treatment method over other conventional method.

Results of the study :

Many researchers and clinicians all over the world were using this innovational technique among the people for giving the rebirth of their younger version to their old ones. PRP therapy includes mainly three steps including, withdrawing the blood of 15-20cc from the patient, then centrifuged to separate the plasma and platelets

from other components and finally after concentrating the platelet rich plasma again injected using microneedle in the needed areas like skin under eyes where the wrinkles are formed in the old people , then in the knee joints and any other ligaments in the body to get faster recovery like within 1 hour of administration and less cosmetic deterioration of the above skin. Alpha granules present in the platelet has abundant growth factors like platelet- derived growth factor[PDGF], Vascular endothelial growth factor[VEGF], Epidermal growth factor[EGF], Fibroblast growth factor [FGF] which helps in the collagen synthesis, angiogenesis, osteoid formation, regulation of inflammation which is needed for the growth and rejuvenation of skin. It is also used in pigmentary diseases for cosmetic purposes to be clear out of those pigmentations found in melasma by decreasing the melanin secretion by EGF and Transforming growth factor [TGF] and in vitiligo by decreasing the apoptosis of melanocytes by stimulating Bcl-2 .It is also used in healing the wounds by collagen synthesis and angiogenesis in wounds like diabetic ulcer and venous leg causes serious damage to the skin in both health as well as cosmetic concern. Both PDGF and VEGF are also used in the alopecia areas thereby promoting hair follicle proliferation. So, hereby PRP therapy has an enormous use in giving rebirth to the skin which got older ,injured tissues to get regenerated and pigmentary disorders can be treated better to get a better cosmetic and healing view got from other techniques.

Conclusion:

Thereby Platelet Rich Plasma [PRP] therapy has a broad use among the skin diseases like pigmentary diseases like melasma and vitiligo, non scarring alopecia and other autoimmune skin diseases in which the skin gets damaged. It is used also used in injuries for sportsmen for faster recovery and less scarring.

Reference:

- 1.)<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC10652151/>
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